

Polynuclear Aromatic Hydrocarbons. Part VII. Synthesis of 3,6-Dimethyltetraphene*

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3,6-Dimethyltetraphene has been synthesised by the Colonge-Mukherji cyclialkylation of naphthalene with 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone. An alternative synthesis of the same hydrocarbon has also been effected through succinoylation of 2,6-dimethyl-1, 2, 3, 4, 9, 10, 4a, 10a-octahydrophenanthrene.

In an earlier communication¹, a synthesis of 6-methyltetraphene by the Colonge-Mukherji cyclialkylation of naphthalene with 2-allylcyclohexanone was reported. By the same procedure 3,6-dimethyltetraphene has now been obtained in satisfactory yield. Naphthalene was condensed with 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in carbon disulphide according to the procedure of Mukherji and Bhattacharyya², when 2-(2'- β -naphthylpropyl)-4-methylcyclohexanone (I) was obtained in 40% yield; it was characterised through its crystalline semicarbazone and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The β -orientation in the naphthalene moiety is based on analogy with the products obtained earlier¹⁻³. The ketone (I) was reduced by aluminium isopropoxide in 75% yield and the resultant alcohol (II) cyclised by concentrated sulphuric acid at 0-5°. Dehydrogenation of the cyclised product (III) with Pd-C furnished 3,6-dimethyltetraphene (IV) in 75% yield, characterised and purified through its picrate and confirmed through its UV and IR spectra. The synthesis was further simplified by cyclodehydration of ketone (I) with polyphosphoric acid or *p*-toluenesulphonic acid³ to the hexahydro derivative (XI), followed by dehydrogenation with Pd-C.

A synthesis of 3,6-dimethyltetraphene was reported earlier⁴ by condensing tetralin with 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone, followed by the same reaction sequences shown in Chart 1. The melting point of the present sample (IV), 115-16°, however, considerably differed from that of the previous one, 145-46°, although the m.p.s of the picrates were the same. This led us to investigate and confirm the structure of our earlier starting material, 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone, prepared through formylation, and to our surprise we found that whereas the 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone of our present sample melted at 115°, the sample reported earlier⁴ melted at 85°. 2-Allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone was also prepared by allylation of the enamine from an authentic sample of 4-methylcyclohexanone and morpholine according to the procedure of Stork *et al.*⁵. The 2,4-DNP of this sample also melted at 115°, undepressed when mixed with our earlier sample⁴. It appears that either the starting allyl ketone used earlier⁴ was different from 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone, or the melting points of its 2,4-DNP and 3,6-dimethyltetraphene were erroneously recorded.

* The simpler nomenclature and numbering of 1,2-benzanthracene, as recommended by E. Clar (*Polycyclic Hydrocarbons*, Academic Press, London, 1964, Vol. I, p. 307), has been adopted.

1. Mukherji *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1965, 42, 176.
2. Mukherji and Bhattacharyya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 1202.
3. Douglas *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 5072.
4. Gandhi *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1967, 34, 168.
5. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 216.

Our earlier experiments⁴ were therefore carefully repeated. The final aromatised compound, thus obtained, melted at 115°, undepressed when mixed with either the above sample (IV) or with the sample of 3,6-dimethyltetraphene obtained by an alternative route as described in the sequel. The melting points of the picrates of all these three samples were the same, 178-79° and remained undepressed when mixed with one another.

CHART I

An alternative synthesis of 3,6-dimethyltetraphene was effected, by following the method of Cook and Haslewood⁶. The starting material, 2,9-dimethyl-1, 2, 3, 4, 9, 10, 4a, 10a-octahydrophenanthrene (V) was prepared according to Colonge and Arsac⁷. To check its structure, it was dehydrogenated with Pd-C to 2,9-dimethylphenanthrene, the m.p. of the picrate of which corresponded to the literature⁸ (138-39°) for this compound. The octahydrophenanthrene (V) was succinoylated with succinic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in benzene at 0° in 88% yield according to the conditions prescribed by Newman and Zahm⁹. The orientation assigned to the resulting keto-acid (VI) is based on analogy with the findings of Cook and Haslewood⁶ although it is immaterial in the present context, since succinoylation at the other alternative position 7 would also result in the same ultimate product.

The keto-acid (VI) was reduced by the modified Clemmensen method¹⁰ to the butyric

6. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 767.

7. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1954, 445.

8. Bergman *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 3226.

9. *Ibid.*, 1948, 65, 1097.

10. Martin, *ibid.*, 1936, 58, 1439.

acid derivative (VII) in 75% yield; it was converted into its acid chloride with thionyl chloride and then cyclized by Johnson's inverse technique¹¹ to obtain the ketone (VIII) in 82% yield. Ketone (VIII) was reduced with sodium and moist ether and the intermediate carbinol (IX) dehydrated to (X) by heating up to 200° with a crystal of iodine. The latter (X) on dehydrogenation with Pd-C provided the desired 3, 6-dimethyltetraphene (IV) which was purified through its picrate. The melting points of both the aromatic hydrocarbon and its picrate, thus obtained, remained undepressed when mixed with our previous samples.

CHART II

*EXPERIMENTAL

2-Allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone

(a). *Formylation Method.*—4-Methylcyclohexanone was prepared by this method according to the conditions laid down by Gandhi *et al.*⁴ The 2,4-DNP was prepared in the usual way and crystallized from ethyl acetate-methanol in yellow needles, m. p. 115°. (Found: N, 16.28. Calo. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$: N, 16.86%).

(b). *Enamine Method.*—4-Methylcyclohexanone (1 M, 112 g.) was dissolved in pure thiophene-free toluene (400 ml) and treated with morpholine (1.5 M, 130 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 12 hr. under Dean and Stark continuous water separator, equipped with a bulb condenser with a drying tube. When collection of water had ceased, toluene and excess of morpholine were removed (till thermometer recorded 140°). The residue was then cooled to the room temperature. The enamine was not isolated, but was used as such for the allylation step.

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected.

11. Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1092.

To the cold solution of 4-methylcyclohexanone-morpholine-enamine (70%, 140 g.) was added dry thiophene-free benzene (400 ml) and then the flask was equipped with a bulb condenser fitted with an adapter with a side tube containing a drying tube, an addition funnel with a drying tube. Allyl bromide (excess, 150 g.) was added gradually. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hr., when a solid, which first separated, melted and became solid again. After cooling to the room temperature, water (300ml) was added and the mixture refluxed again for 2 hr. Thereafter the organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer washed with benzene (2×50 ml.). The combined extracts were washed exhaustively with HCl(dil.), then made free of acid, and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The solvent was removed and the residue distilled in vacuum to yield 80% of the allylated ketone, b.p. 100-105°/10 mm.

The 2, 4-DNP was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol in yellow needles, m.p. 114-15°, undepressed when mixed with the 2, 4-DNP of 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone, obtained by method (a).

2-[2'-(β-Naphthyl)propyl]-4-methylcyclohexanone(I).—Pure naphthalene (20 g.), dissolved in dry CS₂ (60 ml), was subjected to cationoid reaction with 2-allyl-4-methylcyclohexanone (23 g.) in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (40 g.) under the conditions described by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya*. After the usual working up, a viscous oily product (40%, 17 g.) was obtained, b.p. 220°/1 mm. (Found: C, 86.12; H, 8.36. C₂₀H₂₄O requires C, 85.71; H, 8.57%).

The semicarbazone was prepared in the usual way and recrystallised from ethanol in white flakes, m.p. 111-12°. (Found: N, 11.88. C₁₁H₁₂ON₂ requires N, 12.40%).

The 2,4-DNP was prepared in the customary way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol in yellow needles, m.p. 151°. (Found: N, 11.81. C₂₀H₂₈O₄N₄ requires N, 12.17%).

2-[2'-(β-Naphthyl)propyl]-4-methylcyclohexanol(II).—To aluminium isopropoxide, prepared from aluminium foil (3 g.) in isopropanol (80 ml), was dropped the ketone (I) (6g.) and the apparatus set for downward fractional distillation. The distillation was continued till the test for acetone was negative. Isopropanol (30 ml) was again added and the process repeated till the test for acetone was negative. After the usual working up of the contents, a viscous oily product was obtained (66%, 4 g.), b.p. 210°/1 mm. (Found: C, 85.54; H, 9.48. C₂₀H₂₆O requires C, 85.10; H, 9.22%).

3,6-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4, 5,6,As, 12b-octahydrotetraphene (III).—Theo arbincl (II) (3 g.) was treated with H₂SO₄ (d 1.84, 4 ml) at 0°. The contents were mixed intimately and kept at 0-5° for 3 hr. The cherry-brown complex was decomposed by pouring it on iced water. The mixture was extracted with ether; the ethereal layer was washed free of acidic material and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled under vacuum, b.p. 215°/5 mm, yield 2 g. (Found: C, 90.63; H, 8.42. C₂₀H₂₄ requires C, 90.90; H, 9.10%).

3,6-Dimethyltetraphene (IV).—The hydrocarbon (III) (2g.) was smoothly dehydrogenated with 30% Pd-C (0.2 g.) at 300-320° for 4 hr. and then extracted with light petroleum, filtered, and the solvent removed when a viscous semisolid (75%, 1.5 g.) was obtained. The whole product was converted into its picrate and crystallised from ethanol in deep red

needles. The picrate in benzene was passed through an alumina column to regenerate the hydrocarbon which was recrystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture in light yellow flakes, m.p. 115-16° (lit.⁴ m.p. 145-46°). (Found: C, 93.48; H, 5.94. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{16}$: C, 93.75; H, 6.25%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} : 227 m μ (log ϵ , 4.7), 260 m μ (log ϵ , 4.6), 282 m μ (log ϵ , 5.1), 283 m μ (log ϵ , 5.2), 343 m μ (log ϵ , 3.8), 392 m μ (log ϵ , 3.2). ν^{NaCl} : 2050, 1475, 1355, 885, 815, 750 cm^{-1} .

The picrate was prepared in the usual manner and recrystallised from ethanol in red needles, m.p. 177-78° (decomp.) (lit.⁴ m.p. 179-80°, decomp.). (Found: N, 8.73. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{18}O_7N_3$: N, 8.66%).

3, 6-Dimethyltetraphene (IV) through Direct Cyclodehydration of (I)

(a). *Cyclodehydration with p-Toluenesulphonic Acid*.—The ketone (I) (5 g.) was refluxed for 4 hr. in benzene (100 ml) containing anhydrous *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (from 3g. monohydrate) under a Dean and Stark continuous water separator. The cooled solution was washed with aqueous $NaHCO_3$ and water and dried. The solvent was removed; the residue was dissolved in ethanol and treated with Girard's reagent-T (2.5 g.) in the usual way. After working up, a viscous liquid was obtained (61%, 3 g.), b.p. 205°/3 mm.

(b). *Cyclodehydration with Polyphosphoric Acid*³.—The ketone (I) (3 g.) was heated for 30 min. at 90° in benzene (100 ml) with PPA (21 g.). The cooled mixture was added to iced water and the product isolated in the usual manner. The crude product was treated with Girard's reagent-T (1.5 g.) in the usual way. After working up, the distilled product (72%, 2.1 g.), b.p. 205-10°/3-5 mm, was obtained.

The cyclised product (3 g.) from (a) or (b) was treated with Pd-C (30%, 0.3 g.) at 320-40° for 5 hr. After working up in the usual way, solid 3,6-dimethyltetraphene (IV) was obtained (75%, 2.2 g.). It was crystallised from benzene-ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 115-16°, undepressed when mixed with the earlier sample of (IV).

The picrate was prepared in ether and crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 178-79°, undepressed when mixed with the earlier sample.

β -[6-(2,9-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10, 4a, 10a-octahydrophenanthroyl)] propionic Acid (VI).—2,9-Dimethyloctahydrophenanthrene (22 g.) (prepared according to Colonge and Arsac⁷) was dissolved in pure thiophene-free benzene (100 ml) and placed in a three-necked flask equipped with a mercury-sealed stirrer, a condenser with an addition funnel, a guard tube, and a thermometer. To this was introduced pure succinic anhydride (10 g.) and the mixture was cooled to 0°. Anhydrous aluminium chloride (27 g.) was then added in ten instalments during 1 hr., maintaining the temperature at 0°. When the addition was complete, the mixture was stirred for another 5 hr. at 0° when it developed a brown colour. Thereafter the mixture was poured on iced hydrochloric acid with stirring. The benzene layer was separated; the aqueous phase was extracted once with benzene and combined extract and the benzene layer were washed with HCl, followed by water, and steam distilled to remove the solvent. The residue was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, extracted with ether, and the aqueous phase acidified with HCl (dil.) to liberate the free acid as a gummy solid (87.9%, 28 g.) which could not be crystallised. (Found: C, 77.01; H, 8.80. $C_{20}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 76.43; H, 8.28%).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in the usual manner and crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol as yellow crystals, m.p. 164-65°. (Found: N, 10.83. $C_{26}H_{20}O_6N_4$ requires N, 11.37%).

γ -[6-(2,9-Dimethyl-1,2,3,4,9,10,10a,10a-octahydrophenanthryl)]butyric Acid (VII).—The crude keto-acid (VI) (28 g.) was reduced by the Clemmensen method (Martin's modification) with amalgamated zinc (80 g.), toluene (50 ml), glacial acetic acid (150 ml), and HCl (conc., 200 ml) by refluxing the mixture for 30 hr. when almost whole of the zinc dissolved. The mixture was diluted with water, toluene layer separated, and the solvent steam-distilled. The residue was taken up in ether, washed with water, and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate to yield 20 g. (74.7%) of the acid (VII), b.p. 235-40°/5 mm. (Found: C, 79.65; H, 8.99. $C_{20}H_{28}O_2$ requires C, 80.00; H, 9.33%).

3, 6-Dimethyl-8-keto-1,2,3,4, 5, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 4a, 12b-dodecahydrotetraphene (VIII).—The acid (VII) (18 g.) was treated with thionyl chloride (9 ml) in dry benzene (50 ml) and a drop of anhydrous pyridine. The mixture was left overnight and then benzene and excess thionyl chloride were removed at the room temperature under reduced pressure. The acid chloride, thus obtained, was dissolved in benzene (50 ml), cooled to 0°, and then treated with anhydrous stannic chloride (18 ml), maintaining the temperature at 0°; the mixture was shaken well and kept for 30 min. The contents were poured on iced hydrochloric acid with stirring; the benzene layer was separated with ether and the combined extracts were washed twice with HCl (dil.) and then with $NaHCO_3$. After removal of the solvent a viscous oily product was obtained (10.5 g.), b.p. 230-35°/5 mm. (Found: C, 84.73; H, 9.11. $C_{20}H_{26}O$ requires C, 85.10; H, 9.21%).

The 2, 4-DNP was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from ethyl acetate-methanol as bright red crystals, m.p. 234-35° (decomp.). (Found: N, 12.75. $C_{26}H_{20}O_4N_4$ requires N, 12.12%).

3, 6-Dimethyltetraphene (IV).—The ketone (VIII) (10 g.) was reduced with sodium (8 g.) and moist ether (200 ml). Sodium was added in small pieces during 12 hr. Small portions of water were added from time to time to maintain the moderate reaction. The ether layer was separated, washed free of alkali, and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent a viscous oily carbinol was obtained. The carbinol was heated at 200° for 1 hr. with a crystal of iodine to dehydrate it. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether, washed with thiosulphate solution to remove traces of iodine and then with water, and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, a semisolid distilled at 225°/5 mm to yield 6.5 g. (69%) of the hydrocarbon (X).

The above hydrocarbon (3 g.) was smoothly dehydrogenated with Pd-C (30%, 0.3 g.) at 300-340° for 5 hr. in an atmosphere of CO_2 . The mixture was extracted with ether, filtered, and the solvent removed to yield 1.5 g. of a sticky solid. The crude product was converted into its picrate in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol in bright red needles. The purified picrate in benzene was passed through an alumina column to regenerate the hydrocarbon which was crystallised in pale yellow crystals from benzene-ethanol, m.p. 113-14°, undepressed when mixed with the earlier samples. (Found: C, 93.17; H, 6.00. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{18}$: C, 93.76; H, 6.25%).

The *picrate* was crystallised twice from ethanol in bright red needles, m.p. 170-80° (decomp.), undepressed when mixed with the picrates from the earlier samples. (Found: N, 9.31. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{19}O_7N_3$: N, 8.66%).

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